

1 **The value of genomic relationship matrices for estimating inbreeding**

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15

16 **Abstract**

17 **Background**

18 The availability of large-scale genomic data has led to the widespread use of different
19 measures of inbreeding that are obtained from the diagonal elements of genomic
20 relationship matrices. However, there is some arbitrariness in this approach as there is
21 no an explicit theoretical background supporting it. In this study we have investigated
22 the behaviour of measures of inbreeding obtained from five different genomic matrices
23 including the Nejati-Javaremi's allelic relationship matrix (F_{NEJ}), Li and Horvitz's
24 matrix based on excess of homozygosity ($F_{L\&H}$) and VanRaden's (methods 1, F_{VR1} , and
25 2, F_{VR2}) and Yang's (F_{YAN}) genomic relationship matrices. We derive expectations at the

26 population level for the different genomic coefficients assuming a single locus model
27 and use these expectations for explaining patterns of the coefficients computed from
28 thousands of SNP genotypes in a highly inbred population of Iberian pigs.

29

30 **Results**

31 Except F_{NEJ} , the different measures do not match with the original definitions of
32 inbreeding coefficient of Wright (correlation) or Malécot (probability). When these
33 coefficients are interpreted as indicators of variability (heterozygosity) being gained or
34 lost across generations, both F_{NEJ} and $F_{L\&H}$ lead to valid results but this is not the case
35 with F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and F_{YAN} . When variability actually increases, F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and F_{YAN} can
36 indicate that it decreases and when variability decreases, F_{VR1} and F_{VR2} can indicate that
37 it increases. Although variability can be increased relative to a reference base population,
38 this is never possible with F_{YAN} . Finally, these three coefficients can indicate that more
39 variability than that initially existing can be lost which is also unreasonable. The very
40 different patterns observed in the pig population for the different coefficients computed
41 from thousands of SNP genotypes are clearly explained by the expectations derived.

42

43 **Conclusions**

44 Genomic inbreeding coefficients obtained from the diagonal elements of genomic
45 matrices that are routinely used in genomic evaluations can lead to inconsistent results
46 in terms of gain and loss of genetic variability and thus to misleading interpretations.
47 Although these matrices have proved to be very efficient in increasing the accuracy of
48 estimated breeding values from genomic predictions, they do not always provide a
49 useful measure of inbreeding.

50

51 **Background**

52 Inbreeding, the mating of individuals related by ancestry, is a fundamental concept in
53 many areas of biology including animal and plant breeding, human genetics and
54 evolutionary and conservation biology. Inbreeding results in a reduction in genetic
55 diversity as increases homozygosity at the expense of heterozygosity. This increased
56 homozygosity in turns increases the incidence of homozygous recessive defects and
57 decreases population means (the phenomenon known as inbreeding depression) for
58 many quantitative traits, particularly those related with fitness.

59

60 The level of inbreeding of an individual is measured by the inbreeding coefficient
61 that was defined by Wright as the correlation between homologous genes of the two
62 gametes uniting to form the individual [1], and later by Malécot as the probability that
63 two homologous genes at a given locus are identical by descent [2]. The inbreeding
64 coefficient also gives the proportion by which the heterozygosity of an individual is
65 reduced by inbreeding [3], and thus the proportional loss of genetic variation.

66 Classically, the inbreeding coefficient of an individual has been determined by its
67 pedigree. However, the pedigree-based inbreeding coefficient provide only expected
68 proportions of the genome that are identical by descent.

69

70 The level of inbreeding has also been obtained from molecular information such as that
71 contained in high-density single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) arrays. Genomic
72 inbreeding coefficients are more accurate than pedigree-based measures as they capture
73 the variation due to Mendelian sampling and therefore can differentiate among
74 individuals with the same pedigree (e.g. [4]). Genomic measures also allow us to

75 differentiate inbreeding at specific genome regions which is not possible with pedigree-
76 based inbreeding.

77

78 Several methodologies have been proposed for obtaining inbreeding coefficients using
79 genomic data (e.g. [5-8]). However, the theoretical background on which they are based
80 is still unclear. For instance, some of these measures come from matrices used to obtain
81 genomic predictions in animal breeding. In this context, BLUP evaluations are being
82 replaced by GBLUP evaluations by substituting the numerator relationship matrix
83 (NRM) by a variety of genomic relationship matrices (GRMs) [7, 8]. Given that the
84 diagonals of the NRM are 1 plus the inbreeding coefficient, it has been accepted,
85 without any further investigation, that the diagonals of the GRM are 1 plus the realised
86 inbreeding. However, there is no an explicit theoretical background supporting it.
87 Despite this, these genomic measures have been widely used [4, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14,
88 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31]. The proposed genomic
89 estimators of inbreeding can be very different and also the correlations between them
90 vary greatly. Thus, it is timely to investigate their behaviour.

91

92 In this study we compare genomic inbreeding coefficients obtained from different
93 methodologies for understanding their relationship with traditional definitions of
94 inbreeding. First we describe different coefficients obtained from genomic information
95 at the individual level. Second we derive expectations at the population level for the
96 different coefficients assuming a single locus model. Finally, these expectations are
97 used for explaining patterns of the different coefficients computed from thousands of
98 SNP genotypes in a pig population.

99

100 **Individual inbreeding coefficients obtained from genomic data**

101 Individual genome-wide inbreeding coefficients were obtained from the diagonal
102 elements of five different genomic relationship matrices. The coefficients compared are
103 described below.

104

105 1. F_{NEJ} : Inbreeding coefficient computed from the diagonal elements of the allelic
106 relationship matrix of Nejati-Javaremi et al. [6] as

$$107 \quad F_{NEJ} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^S (\sum_{j=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^2 I_{jjk}) / 2}{S} - 1$$

108 where I_{jjk} is the identity of the j th allele with the j th allele at SNP k of the individual
109 and takes the value of 1 if the two alleles are identical and 0 if they are not. Note that
110 F_{NEJ} is simply the proportion of SNPs that are homozygous for the individual.

111

112 2. $F_{L\&H}$: Inbreeding coefficient based on the relationship matrix describing deviations
113 from Hardy-Weinberg proportions. It was computed as

$$114 \quad F_{L\&H} = \frac{SF_{NEJ} - \sum_{k=1}^S [1 - 2p_{k(0)}(1 - p_{k(0)})]}{S - \sum_{k=1}^S [1 - 2p_{k(0)}(1 - p_{k(0)})]}$$

115 where $p_{k(0)}$ is the frequency of the reference allele (allele B) of SNP k in the base
116 (reference) population [5, 32].

117

118 3. F_{VR1} : Inbreeding coefficient computed from the diagonal elements of the genomic
119 relationship matrix obtained according to VanRaden's method 1 [7]. Thus,

$$120 \quad F_{VR1} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^S (x_k - 2p_{k(0)})^2}{2 \sum_{k=1}^S p_{k(0)}(1 - p_{k(0)})} - 1$$

121 where x_k is the genotype of the individual for SNP k that was coded as 0, 1 or 2 for
122 genotypes AA, AB and BB, respectively, and $p_{k(0)}$ is as defined for $F_{L\&H}$.

123

124 4. F_{VR2} : Inbreeding coefficient computed from the diagonal elements of the genomic
125 relationship matrix obtained according to VanRaden's method 2 [7]. Thus,

$$126 \quad F_{VR2} = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{k=1}^S \frac{(x_k - 2p_{k(0)})^2}{2p_{k(0)}(1 - p_{k(0)})} - 1$$

127 where x_k and $p_{k(0)}$ are as in F_{VR1} .

128

129 5. F_{YAN} : Inbreeding coefficient computed from the diagonal elements of the genomic
130 relationship matrix of Yang [8]. Thus,

$$131 \quad F_{YAN} = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{k=1}^S \frac{x_k^2 - (1 + 2p_{k(0)})x_k + 2p_{k(0)}^2}{2p_{k(0)}(1 - p_{k(0)})}$$

132 where x_k and $p_{k(0)}$ are as in F_{VR1} .

133

134 All coefficients depending on allele frequencies (i.e. $F_{L\&H}$, F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and F_{YAN}) were
135 computed using the initial frequencies; i.e., those in the base population.

136

137 The coefficients investigated varied in the ranges in which their values are contained,
138 and, with the exception of F_{NEJ} , these ranges depend on the initial frequency $p_{(0)}$. Given
139 that F_{NEJ} is a proportion (the proportion of homozygous SNPs), it ranges from 0 to 1. At
140 the individual level, values for $F_{L\&H}$ range from $-\infty$ to 1 and those for F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and
141 F_{YAN} range from -1 to ∞ . These ranges for $F_{L\&H}$, F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and F_{YAN} were given in
142 Zhang et al. [18] (see their Figures 3 – 5). When all SNPs are homozygous $F_{L\&H}$ equals
143 1 and when all are heterozygous it ranges from $-\infty$ to -1 . F_{VR1} and F_{VR2} cover all the
144 range (from -1 to ∞) both when all SNPs are homozygous and when all are
145 heterozygous. Finally, when all SNPs are homozygous, F_{YAN} ranges from 0 to ∞ and

146 when all are heterozygous F_{YAN} equals -1 . Thus, values for $F_{L\&H}$, F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and F_{YAN}
147 can be outside the permitted ranges for probabilities and correlations. However, as
148 inbreeding coefficients they still can be interpreted as a loss or gain in variability
149 (heterozygosity) relative to the initial variability at the reference base population.
150 Negative values would indicate a gain in variability and values between 0 and 1 would
151 indicate a loss of variability. Values greater than 1 would indicate that more variability
152 than that existing initially has been lost which is an unreasonable result.

153

154 **Expected genomic inbreeding coefficients at the population level: a**

155 **single locus model**

156 Population expected values for the different coefficients based on genomic relationship
157 matrices were obtained assuming a single SNP model. Specifically, predictions were
158 developed for $F_{L\&H}$, F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and F_{YAN} . It will become clear that values for these
159 coefficients depend on frequency changes.

160

161 Let $p_{(0)}$ be the initial frequency of allele B. After t generations, the frequency will have
162 changed to a value $p_{(t)}$ due to different reasons including random drift and selection.

163 Assuming random mating we can expect that at generation t , genotypic frequencies
164 would be in Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium. Thus, the expected F for a group of
165 individuals belonging to a given generation t , where F is being calculated, can be
166 obtained from

167

$$168 \quad E(F) = [freq(AA)F_{AA} + freq(AB)F_{AB} + freq(BB)F_{BB}],$$

169

170 where $freq(AA) = (1 - p_{(t)})^2$, $freq(AB) = 2p_{(t)}(1 - p_{(t)})$ and $freq(BB) = p_{(t)}^2$ and F_{XY} is
171 the inbreeding coefficient for an individual with genotype XY computed using the
172 initial frequency $p_{(0)}$ as described in the previous section. The whole range of $p_{(0)}$ and
173 $p_{(t)}$ values were used to make predictions.

174

175 We will show now that predictions depend on the initial and current frequencies (i.e.,
176 on the frequency change) and the trends observed for the different coefficients.

177 Predictions for $F_{L\&H}$, F_{VR1} (or F_{VR2}) and F_{YAN} for the whole range of starting ($p_{(0)}$) and
178 current ($p_{(t)}$) frequencies are shown in Figure 1. Note that in a single locus model

179 $E(F_{VR1}) = E(F_{VR2}) = E(F_{VR})$.

180

181 **[Figure 1]**

182

183 The expected $F_{L\&H}$ (Figure 1a) is between $-\infty$ and 1. When the frequency of the minor
184 allele is increased (i.e. $p_{(t)} > p_{(0)}$) towards 0.5, $E(F_{L\&H})$ becomes negative indicating
185 that some variability has been gained. This makes sense given that the maximum
186 variability occurs when the frequency is 0.5. Given that the upper limit of $E(F_{L\&H})$ is 1 it
187 is never expected when using this coefficient that more variability than that initially
188 existing can be lost. $E(F_{L\&H})$ takes the value of 1 when the SNP becomes fixed which is
189 equivalent to say that all variability has been lost.

190

191 The expected F_{VR} calculated from the diagonal of VanRaden's GRMs is within the
192 range $[0, 1]$ for some combinations of $p_{(0)}$ and $p_{(t)}$ but for many other combinations it
193 is outside this range (Figure 1b). In fact, $E(F_{VR})$ ranges from -1 to ∞ . This means that
194 $E(F_{VR})$ can indicate that some variability has been gained but never more than 100% of

195 the initial variability as the lower limit is -1 . It also means that $E(F_{VR})$ can indicate that
196 more than 100% of the initial variability can be lost as it can take values > 1 (up to ∞).

197

198 On the right of Figure 1b the grid of initial and current frequencies is divided in regions
199 where $E(F_{VR})$ is < 0 , between 0 and 1 or > 1 . When the frequency of the minor allele is
200 doubled (i.e., $p_{(t)} = 2p_{(0)}$) but is still less than 0.5 then $E(F_{VR}) = 1$ which means that
201 100% of the variability has been lost in the current generation when in fact variability
202 has increased. For instance, if $p_{(0)} = 0.25$ and $p_{(t)} = 0.5$, F_{VR} indicates that all the initial
203 variability has been lost despite the fact that the maximum variability is at frequency
204 0.5. When the frequency of the minor allele increases more than double (i.e., $p_{(t)} >$
205 $2p_{(0)}$), $E(F_{VR})$ becomes > 1 (for instance, for $p_{(0)} = 0.1$ and $p_{(t)} = 0.3$, $E(F_{VR}) = 2.2$)
206 which indicates that more than 100% of the initial variability has been lost which is
207 unreasonable. On the other hand, when the initial frequency of the minor allele is < 0.33
208 and this minor allele becomes rarer then $E(F_{VR}) < 0$, indicating that variability has
209 increased relative to its initial value. This is also the case when the minor allele is lost
210 ($p_{(t)} = 0$). Thus, although in principle, under these scenarios variability in the current
211 generation is lower than in the initial generation, $E(F_{VR})$ indicates that some variability
212 has been gained which does not make any sense either.

213

214 Although for a particular individual in the population, F_{YAN} can be negative (up to -1),
215 contrary to $E(F_{VR})$, the expected F_{YAN} calculated from the diagonal of Yang's GRM is
216 never less than 0 (it ranges from 0 to ∞ ; Figure 1c) indicating that heterozygosity cannot
217 be higher than that existing initially. However, heterozygosity can indeed increase
218 relative to its initial value. On the other hand, and as $E(F_{VR})$, $E(F_{YAN})$ can be greater than
219 1 meaning that more heterozygosity than that existing initially can be lost. Also,

220 although in principle increasing the frequency of the rare allele towards 0.5 leads to an
221 increase in variability, $E(F_{YAN})$ can indicate that variability has been reduced. For
222 instance, for scenarios where $p_{(0)} = 0.1$, if the frequency stays at 0.1 in the current
223 generation, $E(F_{YAN}) = 0$ but if the frequency moves to 0.2, $E(F_{YAN})$ becomes greater than
224 0 ($E(F_{YAN}) = 0.11$) indicating that some variability has been lost, and if it moves to 0.5
225 (in theory where variability is maximum), $E(F_{YAN})$ becomes greater than 1 ($E(F_{YAN}) =$
226 1.78) indicating that more than 100% of the initial variability has been lost.

227

228 When the initial frequency ($p_{(0)}$) is set to 0.5, the expected value for $F_{L\&H}$, F_{VR} and F_{YAN}
229 is the same independently of the current frequency ($p_{(t)}$) (see Additional file 1). In this
230 scenario all three coefficients range from 0 (when $p_{(t)}$ stays at 0.5) to 1 (when the SNP
231 becomes fixed; i.e., $p_{(t)} = 0$ or 1).

232

233 Figure 2 shows profiles of Figure 1 for the specific cases where the reference allele is
234 driven to a frequency of 0, 0.5 or 1 in the current generation. For any value of the initial
235 frequency, $E(F_{L\&H}) = 1$ when the SNP becomes fixed ($p_{(t)} = 0$ or 1), as expected
236 (Figures 2a and 2c). However, when the major allele is lost (Figure 2a) or when the
237 minor allele is fixed (Figure 2c) both $E(F_{VR})$ and $E(F_{YAN})$ take values above 1 (in fact
238 their upper limit is ∞). Losing the minor allele leads to negative values for $E(F_{VR})$ when
239 $p_{(0)} < 1/3$ and its limit is in -1 (Figure 2a). Similarly, fixing the major allele leads to
240 negative values for $E(F_{VR})$ when $p_{(0)} > 2/3$ and its limit is also in -1 (Figure 2c). In
241 these scenarios, $E(F_{YAN})$ stays at 1. It is very interesting to note that when $p_{(t)} = 0.5$,
242 $E(F_{YAN})$, and to a lesser extent $E(F_{VR})$, behaves as a mirror image of $F_{L\&H}$ (Figure 2b).

243

244 In summary, when the inbreeding coefficient is interpreted as an indicator of loss or
245 gain of variability, $F_{L\&H}$ gives sensible values but this is not the case with F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and
246 F_{YAN} . In fact, $E(F_{L\&H})$ follows the trend of loss/gain in heterozygosity due to changes in
247 allele frequencies. When the MAF is reduced (i.e., when heterozygosity is reduced
248 relative to a reference base population) $E(F_{L\&H})$ increases. However, $E(F_{VR1})$ and
249 $E(F_{VR2})$ which can lead us to think i) that more than 100% of the initial variability can
250 be lost; and even worse ii) that variability has increased when in reality it has decreased
251 and the opposite (that variability has decreased when in reality it has increased). $E(F_{YAN})$
252 is also inconsistent as it can never indicate that variability has increased and can indicate
253 that more than 100% of the initial variability is lost.

254

255 **[Figure 2]**

256

257

258 **Patterns of genomic inbreeding coefficients obtained from a high-**
259 **density SNP panel in a population of Guadyerbas pigs**

260 Having provided expected values for the different coefficients assuming a single locus
261 we will now investigate whether our interpretations reflect what is observed with real
262 data when thousands of SNPs are used to compute the coefficients in a population of
263 Iberian pigs.

264

265 **Pig samples and SNP genotypes**

266 Data used to investigate patterns of inbreeding with different genomic measures
267 originated from a herd of Guadyerbas Iberian pigs. The Guadyerbas strain is one of the
268 most ancient surviving Iberian strains. It is highly inbred and in serious danger of

269 extinction. The strain was originated from 4 males and 20 females [33] and was
270 conserved from 1944 until 2011 in an experimental herd as a genetically isolated
271 population. Accurate and complete genealogy is available from the establishment of the
272 herd (about 25 generations) and includes 1,178 animals born from 197 sires and 467
273 dams.

274

275 All animals for which DNA samples were available were genotyped with the Illumina
276 PorcineSNP60 BeadChip v1. They included 86 males and 141 females born in the herd
277 between 1992 and 2011. SNP positions in the genome were based on the genome
278 assembly Sscrofa 11.1. Quality control procedures are described in Saura et al. [12].
279 The final number of samples and SNPs retained after quality control were 219 and
280 47,120, respectively. The generation interval is about three years and so for the analysis
281 of genomic inbreeding, we considered six cohorts of animals born in successive periods
282 of three years, starting from year 1994 (Table 1).

283

284 **[Table 1]**

285

286 **Patterns of genomic inbreeding coefficients**

287 Genomic coefficients were obtained for all genotyped pigs using the SNPs segregating in
288 cohort 1 (17,951 SNPs). Frequencies used to obtain coefficients $F_{L\&H}$, F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and F_{YAN}
289 were those in cohort 1 (i.e., this cohort was considered to be the base population).

290

291 Summary statistics for the different inbreeding coefficients, computed at the individual
292 level, are given in Table 2 for first and last cohorts. The proportion of homozygous loci
293 (F_{NEJ}) increased by about 9% from cohort 1 to cohort 6. F_{NEJ} had a much higher average

294 and a lower standard deviation than the other coefficients. Coefficients weighted by the
295 initial frequencies (i.e. $F_{L\&H}$, F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and F_{YAN}) were on average below 0 at cohort 1
296 (about -0.1) and became positive (up to 0.2) at cohort 6. Pairwise correlations between
297 coefficients (Figure 3) ranged from 0.4 to 1 in cohort 1 and from 0.7 to 1 in cohort 6. As
298 expected, the correlation between F_{NEJ} and $F_{L\&H}$ was 1 . Very high correlations (above
299 0.9) were also found between F_{YAN} and F_{NEJ} , F_{YAN} and $F_{L\&H}$, F_{YAN} and F_{VR1} , and F_{VR1}
300 and F_{VR2} . The lowest correlations were between F_{VR2} and F_{NEJ} and F_{VR2} and $F_{L\&H}$. These
301 increased from about 0.4 in cohort 1 to about 0.7 in cohort 6 and this could be due to
302 losses of rare alleles across time but also to random fluctuations.

303

304

[Table 2]

305

306 A sliding window approach was used for determining patterns of inbreeding across the
307 genome. Each chromosome was divided into sliding windows of 35 SNPs (average
308 length of 4.25 Mb), and then the average F was computed within each window, that was
309 moved one SNP at a time. For coefficients depending on allele frequencies ($F_{L\&H}$, F_{VR1} ,
310 F_{VR2} and F_{YAN}), formulae were applied within each window. Finally, values were
311 averaged across individuals.

312

313

[Figure 3]

314

315 The evolution of homozygosity clearly varied across chromosomes and across regions
316 within chromosomes (Figure 4). SNPs still segregating at cohort 1 became fixed at cohort
317 6 in several genome regions (see for instance SSC4, SSC8, SSC13, SSC14 and SSC17).

318

319 Figure 5 compares patterns of the different coefficients across the genome for cohort 6.
320 Only SNPs segregating at cohort 1 were considered here. In general, patterns for the
321 different coefficients differ greatly. It is interesting to note that those for F_{VR1} and F_{VR2}
322 were in general like mirror images of $F_{L\&H}$ patterns. Particularly striking is the fact that
323 in regions where SNPs have become fixed (see also Figure 4), $F_{L\&H}$ was 1 while F_{VR1}
324 and F_{VR2} were negative with large absolute values. Two very clear examples can be
325 observed in the region between 43 and 56 Mb of SSC4 and the region between 58 and
326 82 Mb of SSC14. In both regions, the initial frequency of the minor allele was very low
327 ($p_{(0)} \leq 0.1$) and at cohort 6 the allele had been already lost ($p_{(t)} = 0$). In all positions
328 within these regions $F_{L\&H}$ was 1 while F_{VR1} and F_{VR2} became negative (about -0.8 in the
329 SSC4 region and ranging from -0.9 to -0.6 in the SSC14 region) suggesting that some
330 variability had been gained, and F_{YAN} had low values (about 0.1 in the SSC4 region and
331 ranging from 0.1 to 0.2 in the SSC14 region). These observations agree with the
332 expectations describe above and lead us to conclude that $F_{L\&H}$ is a much more valuable
333 measure of variability change than F_{VR1} or F_{VR2} . In these regions where all variability
334 had been lost, $F_{L\&H}$ indicates that this is the case but both F_{VR1} and F_{VR2} indicate that
335 variability has been gained.

336

337 **[Figure 4]**

338

339 **[Figure 5]**

340

341 Also, there are regions where variability increased from cohort 1 to cohort 6 as F_{NEJ} was
342 lower in the latter (Figure 4). Some examples include regions between 102 and 112 Mb
343 of SSC3, between 41 and 72 Mb of SSC6 and between 81 and 97 Mb of SSC13. In all

344 these cases, $F_{L\&H}$ showed indeed this increase in variability as it became negative.
345 However, F_{VR1} and F_{VR2} were again like mirror images of $F_{L\&H}$ while F_{YAN} although
346 positive was close to 0. These observations also agree with the expectations. For
347 instance, the average $p_{(0)}$ and $p_{(t)}$ in the SSC13 region were 0.31 and 0.40, respectively.
348 With this frequency change, $-1 < E(F_{L\&H}) < 0$ while expected values for F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and
349 F_{YAN} are all between 0 and 1. It is also remarkable the high peaks observed for F_{VR2} . In
350 some regions of SSC2 and SSC17, F_{VR2} reached a value as high as 4. In these regions
351 (between 35 and 38 Mb in SSC2 and between 33 and 34 Mb in SSC17) there are SNPs
352 that go from a very low frequency ($p_{(0)} < 0.1$) to a frequency higher than 0.3 and
353 expectations tell us that, under these circumstances, F_{VR2} reaches very high positive
354 values (Figure 1b) while $F_{L\&H}$ becomes negative (Figure 1a).

355

356 With VanRaden's and Yang's coefficients, and in particular VanRaden' method 2, a
357 higher inbreeding coefficient is assigned to an individual homozygous for a rare allele
358 than to an individual homozygous for a common allele. Thus, F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and F_{YAN} give a
359 higher weight to those SNPs with low MAF. Given this, in addition to the scenario
360 considered so far where all SNPs segregating at cohort 1 ($MAF > 0$) were used to obtain
361 the inbreeding coefficients, two additional scenarios that varied in the MAF cut-off
362 points were analysed: i) using only common variants (here defined as SNPs with MAF
363 > 0.05); and ii) using only very common variants (here defined as SNPs with MAF $>$
364 0.25). This allowed to determine how the differences among coefficients vary in the
365 different MAF scenarios.

366

367 Figure 6 shows patterns of the different coefficients computed using only SNPs with
368 MAF > 0.05 or MAF > 0.25 for three chromosomes. When only SNPs with MAF > 0.05

369 at cohort 1 were used, some of the strong peaks shown particularly by F_{VR2} disappeared
370 (Figure 6 versus Figure 5). Including stricter MAF filters ($MAF > 0.25$) led to very
371 similar patterns for all inbreeding coefficients (Figure 6). In fact, pairwise correlations
372 between the different coefficients increased considerably relative to those showed in
373 Figure 3. When using only SNPs with $MAF > 0.25$, all correlations were ≥ 0.95 both in
374 cohort 1 and 6. SNPs with $MAF > 0.05$ and $MAF > 0.25$ represented respectively 92
375 (16,532 SNPs) and 54% (9,716 SNPs) of the total number of segregating SNPs at cohort
376 1. Note that SNP density greatly decreased in some regions when SNPs are filtered for
377 MAF and so there are discontinuities in the Figure. These results show that
378 inconsistencies described earlier for F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and F_{YAN} occur when there are SNPs
379 with low MAF but these SNPs really exist in practice.

380

381

[Figure 6]

382

383

384 **Discussion**

385 The inbreeding coefficient has been defined as a probability [2] or as a correlation [1]
386 and thus its legitimate range is between 0 and 1 or -1 and 1, respectively. Another
387 interpretation of the inbreeding coefficient, that has been used here, is in terms of loss or
388 gain of variability relative to a reference base population. Under this interpretation, a
389 negative value (even a value lower than -1) makes sense and means that some
390 variability has been gained. On the other hand, a value higher than 1 means that more
391 variability than that initially existing has been lost which is unreasonable. Using a single
392 locus model, we have provided expectations for different genomic inbreeding
393 coefficients that have been widely used in the literature. These expectations have helped

394 understanding the patterns observed for the different coefficients when they are
395 computed using thousands of SNPs in a pig population. Except F_{NEJ} , none of the other
396 genomic coefficients considered here (i.e. those depending on allele frequencies) match
397 with Malécot's definition of inbreeding coefficient (probability) or with Wright's
398 definition (correlation) as they can be out of the legitimate ranges [31]. In fact, at the
399 individual level, $F_{L\&H}$ ranges from $-\infty$ to 1 and F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and F_{YAN} range from -1 to ∞ .
400 At the population level (see the section on expected genomic coefficients under a single
401 locus model above), ranges are the same except for F_{YAN} that ranges from 0 to ∞ . When
402 these coefficients are interpreted as indicators of whether variability is gained or lost
403 across generations, $F_{L\&H}$ leads to sensible results but this is not the case with F_{VR1} , F_{VR2}
404 and F_{YAN} .
405
406 It is well known that the highest variability (heterozygosity) occurs at frequencies 0.5.
407 Although $F_{L\&H}$ is not a probability or a correlation, this coefficient is useful for
408 determining when variability is lost or gained. When a rare allele increases its
409 frequency, $F_{L\&H}$ indicates that variability is gained, as expected. Also, this coefficient
410 never indicates that more variability than that existing in the initial generation can be
411 lost. However, F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and F_{YAN} do not match either with a definition related with the
412 proportion of variability lost or gained. In fact, for some $p_{(0)}$ and $p_{(t)}$ combinations,
413 these three coefficients can indicate that variability is lost when a minor allele increases
414 its frequency towards 0.5 and this loss of variability can be even higher than 100% of
415 the initial variability. Moreover, F_{VR1} and F_{VR2} can take values that indicate that
416 heterozygosity in the current generation is higher than that existing initially although
417 some heterozygosity has actually been lost. This does not occur with F_{YAN} at the

418 population level as $E(F_{YAN})$ is never negative; i.e. it always indicates that heterozygosity
419 decreases although in theory it could increase.
420
421 One of the advantages of using genomic rather than pedigree data to evaluate inbreeding
422 is the possibility of investigating its patterns across the genome. Here we have evaluated
423 patterns of the different genomic coefficients computed from thousands of SNPs
424 obtained with the Illumina PorcineSNP60 BeadChip v1 in a population of Iberian pigs.
425 This population is highly inbred and has a pedigree-based effective population size (N_e)
426 as low as 20.5 animals. The behaviour of the different coefficients observed with real
427 data are explained well by the expectations developed. In six generations (i.e., from
428 cohort 1 to cohort 6) many SNPs became fixed (see Figure 4). This loss of variability
429 observed using F_{NEJ} (that is simply the proportion of homozygous SNPs) was clearly
430 reflected in the value for $F_{L\&H}$ ($F_{L\&H} = 1$). However, the negative values for F_{VR1} and
431 F_{VR2} could indicate that variability in cohort 6 is higher than in cohort 1. On the other
432 hand, regions where variability increased from cohort 1 to cohort 6 showed negative
433 values for $F_{L\&H}$ (indicating correctly what happened) but positive values for F_{VR1} , F_{VR2}
434 and F_{YAN} (indicating the opposite). Although in some circumstances $E(F_{YAN})$ predicts
435 that variability can be gained, this occurs when in fact variability has been lost. In
436 general, F_{VR1} and F_{VR2} behave similarly although values for F_{VR2} are more extreme.
437 Values for F_{YAN} are not so extreme and lie between those for $F_{L\&H}$ and those for F_{VR1}
438 and F_{VR2} , and generally, are close to 0. Given these results, it is clear that care should be
439 taken when deciding the genomic coefficient chosen when specific genome regions are
440 targeted for controlling inbreeding.

441

442 Here we have analysed the behaviour of five different genomic measures of inbreeding
443 that have been widely used in the literature. However, other measures have been
444 proposed (see for instance the review by Kardos et al. [21]). For instance, both PLINK
445 [34] and GCTA [10] software provide a modification of $F_{L\&H}$ (their F^H , here referred to
446 as $F_{L\&H2}$). Although to our knowledge $F_{L\&H2}$ is not used, it is interesting to note that the
447 difference between $F_{L\&H}$ and $F_{L\&H2}$ is equivalent to the difference between F_{VR1} and
448 F_{VR2} in that it only lies on how summation over SNPs is carried out. This can be clearly
449 seen in Guadyerbas patterns shown in Additional file 2. Patterns for $F_{L\&H}$ are in
450 general mirror images of F_{VR1} patterns and patterns for $F_{L\&H2}$ are in general mirror
451 images of F_{VR2} patterns. Another widely used measure of genomic inbreeding not
452 considered here is that based on continuous runs of homozygosity (ROH). Given that
453 this measure (F_{ROH}) is the proportion of the genome that is in ROH, its values range
454 from 0 to 1. Also, F_{ROH} has the advantage that it permits to distinguish between distant
455 (computed with short ROH) and recent inbreeding (computed with long ROH).
456 However, the computation of F_{ROH} requires that markers are mapped. Another
457 disadvantage (the main disadvantage) of this measure is the arbitrariness in the choice of
458 the different parameters needed to define a ROH (e.g. number of heterozygous
459 genotypes permitted in a ROH, minimum SNP density required, maximum distance
460 allowed between two consecutive homozygous SNPs and minimum number of SNPs).
461 Given this, population-wide predictions for F_{ROH} are difficult. Also, due to this
462 arbitrariness F_{ROH} can not lead to an interpretation of loss or gain in heterozygosity as
463 some IBD segments would not be included in its calculation. Finally, there is still
464 controversy about the ability of F_{ROH} for detecting inbreeding depression when
465 compared with other metrics such as $F_{L\&H}$ or F_{YAN} [25, 28, 35, 36].
466

467 The pedigree-based numerator relationship matrix, NRM [37] has been used very
468 extensively for many years to estimate genetic covariances between individuals to be
469 genetically evaluated via BLUP. With the advent of genomic evaluations [38] the NRM
470 has been replaced by more precise realised relationship matrices. This has led to an
471 increased accuracy of predicted breeding values (e.g. [39]). Replacing NRM with GRM
472 has also led to two further applications. The first application has been the object of this
473 study. Given that self-relationships in NRM are expected to be equal to 1 plus
474 inbreeding, genomic inbreeding coefficients have been also obtained from the diagonals
475 of GRMs. However, as we have shown here, this is not always justified. The second
476 application has been based on the fact that the NRM is equal to twice the coancestry
477 matrix and as such it has been used for optimising contributions applying the optimal
478 contribution method (OC) for maintaining genetic variability and avoiding inbreeding
479 depression [40, 41, 42]. In this context, GRMs have been used in OC, replacing NRM.
480 de Cara et al. [43] and Gomez-Romano et al. [44] showed that the coancestry matrix
481 computed from Nejati-Javaremi 's GRM led to higher genetic diversity (measured as
482 expected heterozygosity) maintained than using pedigree-based coancestry matrix.
483 Morales-González et al. [31] showed that the amount of genetic variability retained was
484 higher when using Nejati-Javaremi's or Li and Horvitz's matrices than when using
485 VanRaden and Yang's GRMs although the latter were also efficient in controlling the
486 loss of genetic diversity. Thus, in the context of optimising contributions for
487 maintaining diversity, VanRaden and Yang's GRMs are still useful. In fact, it has been
488 suggested [45] that although leading to less variability maintained, the use of VanRaden
489 and Yang's GRMs in OC could lead to allele frequencies that are closer to those in the
490 original population (i.e., allele frequencies would tend to be unchanged) that may be

491 another objective in conservation programmes, particularly in ex situ conservation
492 programmes where the final aim is the reintroduction to the wild [46].
493
494 As we have already indicated, the Guadyerbas strain is highly inbred and in serious
495 danger of extinction, with an estimate of N_e of 20.5 obtained from the rate of pedigree-
496 based inbreeding. Estimates of N_e obtained from rates of F_{NEJ} and $F_{L\&H}$ from cohort 1 to
497 cohort 6 were both 21.8 (i.e., only slightly higher than the estimate obtained from very
498 accurate pedigree data). Those obtained from F_{VR1} ($N_e = 15.3$) and F_{VR2} ($N_e = 12.4$) were
499 substantially lower and the estimate from F_{YAN} had an intermediate value ($N_e = 18.4$).
500 These results are in agreement with those discussed in the previous sections. As
501 discussed above, the different GRMs would be efficient in preserving genetic variability
502 via the OC method in conservation programmes applied to endangered populations such
503 as the Guadyerbas population. However, Toro et al. [47] have recently questioned the
504 meaning of N_e , one of the key concepts in quantitative and population genetics, when
505 these matrices are used in OC. In particular, when optimal management is carried out
506 using marker information, genetic diversity can increase across generations implying
507 negative estimates of N_e . Also, in the long term, the genomic N_e does not attain an
508 asymptotic value but it shows an unpredictable behaviour. Although their finding were
509 based on computer simulations using Nejati-Javaremi's GRM the same results could be
510 expected with other GRMs.
511
512 It has been suggested that the use of whole genome sequence (WGS) data would
513 produce improved genomic inbreeding coefficient estimates [14] and then it is justified
514 to replace SNP data by WGS data. This would be due to the fact that when compared to
515 SNP panels, WGS captures the many variants with rare alleles not covered by the latter

516 due to their ascertainment bias. However, it would be expected that including a higher
517 proportion of variants with rare alleles will lead to even more inconsistent results than
518 those shown here when using F_{YAN} and F_{VR1} , and particularly F_{VR2} .

519

520 Under the infinitesimal model, the NRM is a matrix of covariances of breeding values
521 but importantly it also is twice the coancestry matrix which contain self-coancestries in
522 the diagonal. Given that the relationship between the self-coancestry (f) and inbreeding
523 (F) coefficients is $f = 0.5(1 + F)$, the NRM provide estimates of F . GRMs are also
524 covariance matrices that have proven to work very well in genomic predictions.

525 However, the theoretical background on which the assumption that inbreeding
526 coefficients can be obtained from the diagonal of GRMs is still unclear. Although F_{NEJ}
527 and $F_{L\&H}$ indicate correctly when variability is lost or gained this is not the case with
528 F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and F_{YAN} .

529

530 **Conclusions**

531 Except for F_{NEJ} (that ranges from 0 to 1), values for the genomic coefficients
532 investigated here are out of ranges corresponding to Malécot's and Wright's definitions
533 of coefficient of inbreeding. When using a third interpretation of inbreeding in terms of
534 loss or gain of variability, $F_{L\&H}$ gives sensible values but this is not the case with F_{VR1} ,
535 F_{VR2} and F_{YAN} . In fact, the expectations derived here at the population level show some
536 inconsistency problems with these three coefficients. These include indications that i)
537 more variability than that initially existing can be lost (F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and F_{YAN}); ii)
538 variability has decreased when in reality it has increased (F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and F_{YAN}); iii)
539 variability has increased when in reality it has decreased (F_{VR1} , F_{VR2}); and iv) it is not
540 possible to gain more variability than that existing initially (F_{YAN}). These problems get

541 smaller when only SNPs with high MAF are used. The expectations developed explain
542 clearly patterns of the different coefficients observed in a highly inbred pig population
543 when using thousands of SNP genotypes.

544

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550

551 **Authors’ contributions**

552 BV and RPW conceived and designed the study. AF performed the analyses and
553 constructed the figures. BV wrote the first draft of the manuscript. All authors
554 contributed to the discussion of results and the edition of the manuscript revision.

555

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565

566 **Availability of data and material**

567 The datasets analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding
568 author on reasonable request.

569

570 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

571 Ethic Committee approval was not obtained for this study as no new animals were
572 handled in this experiment. Analyses were performed using data previously collected
573 with approval by the INIA Scientific Ethic Committee. Animal manipulations were
574 performed according to the Spanish Policy for Animal Protection RD1201/05, which
575 meets the European Union Directive 86/609 about the protection of animals used in
576 experimentation.

577

578 **Consent for publication**

579 Not applicable.

580

581 **Competing interests**

582 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

583

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708

709 **Figure legends**

710

711 **Figure 1** Expected inbreeding coefficient based on the excess of SNP homozygosity
712 ($F_{L\&H}$, **a**) and expected coefficients computed from the diagonal elements of the
713 genomic relationship matrices of VanRaden (methods 1 and 2; $F_{VR} = F_{VR1} = F_{VR2}$, **b**)
714 and Yang (F_{YAN} , **c**), for the whole range of starting and current frequencies, assuming a
715 single locus model. On the right the figures are represented showing areas particular
716 interest

717

Figure 2 Expected $F_{L\&H}$, F_{VR} ($F_{VR1} = F_{VR2}$) and F_{YAN} at the generation where the
reference allele was lost (**a**), driven to a frequency of 0.5 (**b**) or fixed (**c**) relative to the
initial frequency ($p_{(0)}$). $F_{L\&H}$:

718

719 **Figure 3** Scatter plots for individual inbreeding coefficients F_{NEJ} , $F_{L\&H}$, F_{VR1} , F_{VR2} and
720 F_{YAN} against each other in cohort 1 (open symbols) and 6 (filled symbols), and
721 corresponding correlation coefficients (r)

722

723 **Figure 4** Evolution of the proportion of the genome that becomes homozygous (i.e.,
724 F_{NEJ}) from cohort 1 (grey lines) to cohort 6 (black lines) for the different chromosomes
725 of the Guadyerbas genome when using SNPs with $MAF > 0.00$. The horizontal lines
726 represent averages across the genome

727

728

Figure 5 Patterns of different measures of genomic inbreeding ($F_{L\&H}$:
; F_{VR2} :) in cohort 6 for the different chromosomes of the
Guadyerbas genome when using SNPs with MAF > 0.00 in cohort 1

729

Figure 6 Patterns of different measures of genomic inbreeding ($F_{L\&H}$:
; F_{VR2} :) in cohort 6 for chromosomes SSC1, SSC4 and SSC17 of the
Guadyerbas genome when using SNPs with MAF > 0.05 (**a**) or MAF > 0.25 (**b**) in
cohort 1

730

731

732

733

734 **Table 1 Number of genotyped animals per cohort and sex**

Cohort	Birth year range	Males	Females
1	1994 - 1996	13	18
2	1997 - 1999	10	42
3	2000 - 2002	24	18
4	2003 - 2005	8	19
5	2006 - 2007	9	6
6	2009 - 2011	19	29
Total		83	132

735

736

737 **Table 2 Statistics of the different genomic inbreeding coefficients**

Cohort		Mean	Standard	Minimum	Maximum
			deviation		
1	F_{NEJ}	0.616	0.024	0.580	0.674 ⁷³⁸
	$F_{L\&H}$	-0.095	0.070	-0.198	0.071 ⁷⁴⁰
	F_{VR1}	-0.095	0.076	-0.230	0.119 ⁷⁴¹
	F_{VR2}	-0.088	0.108	-0.279	0.211 ⁷⁴²
	F_{YAN}	-0.088	0.053	-0.165	0.061 ⁷⁴³
6	F_{NEJ}	0.669	0.025	0.631	0.674 ⁷⁴⁴
	$F_{L\&H}$	0.056	0.070	-0.052	0.268 ⁷⁴⁵
	F_{VR1}	0.120	0.079	-0.014	0.417 ⁷⁴⁶
	F_{VR2}	0.175	0.108	0.023	0.609 ⁷⁴⁷
	F_{YAN}	0.090	0.076	-0.014	0.364 ⁷⁴⁸

752 **Additional files**

753 **Additional file 1**

754 File format: PDF

Title: Expected $F_{L\&H}$, F_{VR} ($F_{VR1} = F_{VR2}$) and F_{YAN} at a given current frequency ($p_{(t)}$)

when the initial frequency of the reference allele ($p_{(0)}$) is set to 0.5.

Description: $F_{L\&H}$:

755

756 **Additional file 2**

757 File format: PDF

Title: Patterns of different measures of genomic inbreeding in cohort 6 for the different chromosomes of the Guadyerbas genome when using SNPs with MAF > 0.00 in cohort

1.

Description: $F_{L\&H}$:

758

759

760 Figure 1

761 a

770

771 b

780

781 c

785 figure 2

786

787 **a**

795

796

797 **b**

805

806

807 **c**

814

815

816

817 Figure 3

818

819

820 Figure 4

821

822

823 Figure 5

824

825

826

827 Figure 6

828 a

b

829

830

831

832 Additional File1

833

834

836

837